

Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Research Protocol

Bethan Iley, Open Life Science Limited, United Kingdom. [0000-0002-5813-3303](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5813-3303)

Doaa Abdelkader, The British University in Egypt & Open Science Community Egypt, Egypt.
 [0000-0002-2908-5656](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2908-5656)

Anastasiia Afanaseva, Saarland University, Germany.

Jens Dierkes, University and City Library Cologne, University of Cologne, Germany.
[0000-0002-0121-9261](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0121-9261)

Melanie Imming, IM Studio, the Netherlands. [0000-0003-2376-9755](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2376-9755)

Joyce Kao, Digital Research Academy GmbH, Germany. [0000-0003-2082-6937](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2082-6937)

Christian Meesters, NHR SouthWest, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Germany.
[0000-0003-2408-7588](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2408-7588)

José Francisco Pereira Cardoso, Department of Clinical Sciences, University of Lund,
Sweden. [0000-0002-6201-3996](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6201-3996)

Riva Quiroga, Open Life Science Limited, Chile. [0000-0002-1147-4135](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1147-4135)

Heidi Seibold, Digital Research Academy GmbH, Germany. [0000-0002-8960-9642](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8960-9642)

Deborah Udoh, Open Life Science Limited, Nigeria. [0000-0001-7391-686X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7391-686X)

Yo Yehudi, Open Life Science Limited, United Kingdom. [0000-0003-2705-1724](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2705-1724)

Abstract

The Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp aims to upskill open science advocates in digital marketing and communications, with the intention of making their advocacy more effective. This protocol describes three studies which support the development and evaluation of OSPARK training. The research project will investigate how open science advocates engage in outreach activities, the barriers which limit their engagement, their perceived training needs, and their knowledge and confidence regarding outreach activities. These research questions will be investigated through study 1, a qualitative study in which participants will take part in discussion groups asking open ended questions about their open science outreach, and study 2, a larger scale mixed-methods survey. This project will also evaluate the OSPARK Bootcamp's impact on knowledge, confidence, and self-efficacy regarding outreach activities through study 3, a pretest/posttest questionnaire completed by OSPARK Bootcamp attendees.

Keywords: open science, outreach, communications, marketing, training evaluation

Author Note

Conflicts of interests: We have no known conflicts of interests to declare.

Funding: This work is part of the OSPARK (Open Science Promotion and Advocacy Research Knowledge) Bootcamp project, funded through the OSCARS (Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society) first call. OSCARS is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

Author contributions: Conceptualisation and funding acquisition: I.M., J.K., H.S., and Y.Y. Methodology: B.I., H.S., and R.Q. Project administration: B.I. Resources: D.A., A.A., J.F.P.C., J.D., B.I., C.M., and H.S. Supervision: Y.Y. Writing—original draft: B.I., R.Q., and D.U. Writing—review and editing: B.I., R.Q., H.S., and Y.Y.

Correspondence: Correspondence regarding this article should be addressed to Bethan Iley, team@we-are-ols.org.

Formatting: In Appendices, researcher notes are indicated with *italicised green text*. Such text provides information or context for reviewers and other researchers, such as explaining methodological choices. It will not be included in the survey and should not be visible to participants.

Introduction

Open science is an umbrella term for a set of practices and a movement aiming to make research processes and outputs transparent, reproducible, collaborative, impactful, and inclusive (Cole et al., 2024; UNESCO, 2021; Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018). A range of bottom-up and top-down initiatives, infrastructures, services, and communities (henceforth referred to as “open science initiatives”) have aimed to facilitate the uptake of open science across the research ecosystem and life cycle (Havemann, 2023; Skubera et al., 2025; UNESCO, 2023). However, the uptake is sometimes limited, and open science advocates have reported difficulties getting their work seen, acknowledged, and utilised, particularly when working in low-resource settings (Gagliardi et al., 2015; Chuan-Peng et al., 2025).

In general, scientists report positive attitudes towards, yet a perceived a lack of skills and confidence in, a range of marketing and communications domains, from social media to public engagement (Besley et al., 2015; Boon et al., 2022; Iley, Abdelkader et al., 2025; Poliakoff & Webb, 2007). This means that open science advocates are likely struggling to effectively advertise their offerings, leading to a significant disconnect between availability and awareness.

The Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp aims to bridge this gap by training potential “multipliers” to effectively promote their open science initiatives (see Kao et al., 2025). OSPARK will use iterative development and evaluation to create a course aimed at improving open science advocates’ knowledge, skills, and self-efficacy in evidence-based marketing and communication. The iterative development will occur through an email course and a series of workshops (either stand-alone, or attached to larger events such as conferences). The final training program is expected to consist of online learning sessions and self-paced material, culminating in a two-day in-person “bootcamp”. Across the project, learning materials and examples of our own marketing and communications practice are being published as Open Educational Resources on Zenodo.

This protocol outlines a series of studies which aim to support the development, improvement, and evaluation of the OSPARK training programme.

Present Studies

This research project will consist of three studies. Study 1 will involve a series of workshops piloting the OSPARK training material, including a facilitated discussion element. Study 2 will be a survey of open science advocates, regardless of their involvement in OSPARK. Study 3 will be a pre-post evaluation of OSPARK training sessions. The aims, methodology, and

planned analyses of each study are detailed in their respective sections below.

The research questions addressed by the studies described in this protocol are as follows:

- **RQ1:** How do open science advocates engage in outreach activities, and what barriers prevent them from doing so?
- **RQ2:** What training do open science advocates feel they need in marketing, communications, and outreach activities?
- **RQ3:** How knowledgeable and confident are open science advocates about core concepts in outreach activities?
- **RQ4:** Does the OSPARK training programme improve knowledge and self-efficacy regarding marketing, communications, and outreach activities among open science advocates?

This research programme is exploratory and will use an iterative development cycle. This means that ongoing analyses of workshop data in study 1 will be used to make adjustments to the survey measure in studies 2 and pre-post evaluation in study 3. Furthermore, ongoing analyses of all studies will be used to adjust the OSPARK training material.

Figure 1.

Illustration of OSPARK's iterative development cycle.

Ethics and Open Science Statement

This protocol and its appendices will be shared on Zenodo under a CC-BY license before data collection begins. The protocol should be treated as a pre-registration of the research questions and analysis plans in these studies. The materials, anonymised data, and analysis code for these studies will be released in a publicly accessible GitHub repository under a

CC-BY license.

The proposed research has been developed in line with the British Psychological Society Code of Human Research Ethics (Oates et al., 2021) and UK data protection legislation. Ethical review will be obtained from Pearl IRB¹, an independent US-based institutional review board. Pearl IRB was chosen because OLS does not have its own research ethics committee or institutional review board. Additional reviews will be conducted at collaborator institutions, where required.

Informed consent will be obtained from all participants through the use of digital participant information sheets and consent forms. Two of the three studies will use anonymous data collection with consent forms built into the respective surveys. Study 1, which is a qualitative study using discussion groups, will not be anonymous and will use a standalone digital information sheet and consent form. Identifiable information will only be accessible by the research team. Discussion group outputs will be anonymised before analysis. Please see the associated Data Management Plan (see Appendix 1) for more information about how this study's data will be stored and shared.

Study 1: Qualitative investigation of needs and barriers

Study 1 aims to explore open science advocates' experiences of, and barriers to engaging in, outreach activities (RQ1). It also aims to identify their training needs in relation to outreach, marketing, and communications (RQ2). This study will use qualitative methodology, with the intention of empowering open science advocates to describe their outreach activities, barriers to engaging, and training needs in their own words. The results of this study will be used to inform the development of OSPARK training, as well as being used to iteratively develop studies 2 and 3.

Method

Data will be collected as part of in-person and online workshops within the OSPARK programme. At first, in-person workshops will be attached to conferences as a session or a satellite event, while online workshops will be standalone events conducted via Zoom. Standalone in-person workshops may be conducted later in the research programme, if this is deemed appropriate. Participants in the study will be the open science advocates who

¹ <https://www.pearlirb.com/>

take part in these events. We expect that between two and five workshops will be conducted, encompassing 15-50 participants in total.

Workshops will follow the general structure outlined below, regardless of whether they are online or in-person. However, adaptations to the specific requirements of the event (such as the length of time available within a conference slot) will be made.

Phase 1: Informed Consent

For standalone events, informed consent will be obtained from participants as part of the workshop registration process. Where the workshop is part of a conference and prior registration to the workshop is not possible, informed consent will be obtained before the workshop starts. Participants will be directed to an online form which will provide information and collect informed consent (see Appendix B). Consent data will be stored independently of study data.

Phase 2: Teaching Segment

Each workshop will include a teaching segment of varying lengths. This will use resources from the OSPARK programme to introduce participants to digital outreach, marketing, and communications (for an example, see Iley, Udoh, et al., 2025). All teaching segments will include a mixture of lecture content, interactive activities, and question-and-answer sessions. Some will involve the use of workbooks (see Seibold et al., 2025).

The exact length and content of the teaching segment will vary due to differing requirements between events. Some may provide a very brief 25 minute overview of OSPARK material, while others may be a deeper multi-hour introduction. Furthermore, the OSPARK training materials use an iterative development process, meaning that feedback from participants will inform the direction of the course.

Participants will have the option to submit any notes or artefacts they produce during the training segment through an online form. Where these are submitted, they will be included in the analysis after anonymisation.

Phase 3: Discussion Groups

Small discussion groups will then be formed, each containing 2-10 participants and (where available) one facilitator. The strategy used to assign groups will depend on the format and requirements of the workshop—online workshops will likely randomly assign participants to breakout rooms, while in-person workshops will likely group participants based on their seating location.

The facilitator will act as notetaker; where there is no facilitator available, participants will be asked to take notes as a collective. The facilitator and group will be provided a Google Doc

with instructions and a template for note-taking, including a semi-structured list of questions (see Appendix 3). It will be emphasised that this is a flexible list, and that if the group talks about something related which is not directly on the list but still relevant to the research aims, they may explore this. Where a facilitator is present, they will be encouraged to ask open questions if the discussion develops in a way which is not covered by the schedule.

Discussions will be recorded, where possible. In these cases, the recording transcripts will form the basis for data analysis, with notes submitted by participants supplementing this. If a workshop cannot be recorded, such as due to technical difficulties, analysis will be conducted using the submitted notes. Participants will optionally be able to submit artefacts, such as their notes and workbooks from the training segment, using a Google Form hosted by OLS's Google Workspace. These artefacts may be used to supplement the analysis.

Analytic Plan

A thematic analysis of all textual data (transcripts, discussion notes, and any submitted artefacts) will be conducted. A primary researcher will lead the analysis, with additional researchers involved in coding a sample of the data and reviewing coding decisions. Codes and themes will be discussed with the broader project team to facilitate the inclusion of alternative perspectives.

Thematic analysis will be conducted based on the method described by Braun and Clarke (2006). This will be an ongoing process, such that a mini-analysis will be conducted after each workshop, but a final analysis will also take place which combines all data.

Each mini-analysis will involve three steps. First, the researchers will familiarise themselves with the dataset by reading, re-reading, and anonymising the data. Transcripts of online workshops will be captured using Otter.ai, and local automated transcription in DaVinci Resolve Studio will be used for offline workshops; to aid familiarisation, the researchers will correct any inaccuracies in these transcripts using the recordings. Secondly, the researchers will decide the unit of analysis and generate initial codes by reading through a sample of the dataset again and systematically applying labels which describe how they identify meaning within data. The researchers will then discuss the unit of analysis and proposed labels to refine definitions and to agree on a shared understanding of each code. A coding protocol will be developed to document these agreed-upon codes and their applications. Following this, the researchers will independently annotate another sample of the data to assess inter-coder reliability and ensure consistency in the application of the coding framework. Once acceptable reliability is established, the researchers will proceed to code the remainder of the dataset using the coding protocol. Regular meetings will be held throughout the coding process to address ambiguities, updates to the coding protocol, and maintain alignment in the application of codes. Third, the codes will be extracted and

organised to identify potential themes. These potential themes will be shared with the wider research team for feedback. Descriptive information related to course development will also be provided.

In the final analysis, all data will be combined and steps 1-3 applied. After this, the themes will be reviewed and refined, considering both the researchers' understanding of the data and the feedback from the broader research team. A thematic map will be created and again shared with the research team for feedback. Finally, each theme will be refined. A clear name and definition will be written for each, and illustrative examples of data extracts provided. The analysis will be again reviewed during the writing of the final report.

Study 2: Survey of needs, barriers, and knowledge

Study 2 will consist of a larger scale online survey. This aims to assess the landscape of outreach knowledge and activities within the open science movement before a dedicated training programme has been established, expanding upon a prior pilot study (Iley, Abdelkader, et al., 2025). Specifically, study 2 will investigate RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3.

Method

A minimum of 77 participants² will be recruited through existing spaces where open science advocates congregate, such as relevant conferences, online communities, and mailing lists. Individuals will be eligible to participate if they self-report as having any history of involvement in at least one open science or related initiative, service, network, or infrastructure in any capacity. Participants will be excluded if they fail ≥ 2 of the three attention checks embedded throughout the survey. Data collection will stop two weeks after the second OSPARK Bootcamp in-person workshop, which is currently planned for 23rd-24th July 2026.

The survey will include both quantitative and qualitative elements (see Appendix 5 for full materials). It will be conducted using a Google Form hosted on OLS's Google Workspace, and data will be recorded anonymously. The survey will primarily be conducted in English but may be translated into other official languages of the European Union.

² An a priori power analysis was conducted using WebPower (Zhang & Yuan, 2018). As six correlations will be conducted, a Bonferroni adjusted p -value of $.05/6 = .0083$ was utilised. To achieve 80% power at the $r = .40$ level, a minimum sample size of 69.57 would be required. 10% has been added to this to account for potential low-quality responses. There is no upper bound on sample size provided as greater responses will provide more diverse qualitative insights.

Upon clicking the survey URL, participants will be taken to an embedded participant information sheet and consent form. The participant information sheet will provide information about the purpose of the study, what the survey will involve, who can participate, and how data will be collected and stored. Participants will be required to respond to a bot detection task embedded into the survey. Those who pass the bot detection task and provide their consent will move to the full survey.

On the second page of the survey, participants will answer a series of questions about their current and future outreach activities, drawn from Iley, Abdelkader et al. (2025). A definition will be provided for "outreach activities" to minimise the effects of different individual understandings of what this may involve—this definition will be repeated throughout the survey.

On the third page, participants will be asked about barriers to engaging in open science outreach, marketing, and communications activities they have experienced. Participants will be presented with a list of potential barriers, split into three categories: Knowledge and skills, prioritisation and resources, and community and environment (Iley, Abdelkader et al., 2025). Participants will be able to select as many or as few choices as they wish, and will also be able to submit additional barriers through a "something else (please specify)" open text response option.

On the fourth page, participants will complete a series of questions aiming to assess whether participants' approach to outreach, marketing, and communications aligns with the OSPARK course content. Nine questions have been drafted, which will be pre-tested using a separate questionnaire (see Appendix 4).

The fifth page intends to assess participants' self-efficacy for conducting outreach activities. This will be measured using the General Self-Efficacy Scale (Chen et al., 2001) as well as an additional self-report of confidence in conducting outreach activities.

The sixth page will involve participants responding to two open response questions aiming to identify their training needs. They will be asked about training and resources they have already accessed, and their preferences for knowledge or skill development.

Finally, participants will be asked to report demographic data: their length of involvement with open science, career stage, regions of residence during childhood and at present, and preferred communications platforms. Participants will then be shown a closing message with study information as a post-submission message.

Analytic Plan

Frequencies and percentages will be calculated for all categorical and Likert scale variables. Visualisations will be created to facilitate comparison of responses to the self-efficacy and

knowledge measures across different demographic groups. The research team will examine patterns within these visualisations, with particular attention to potential disparities or similarities across groups. Additionally, six correlations will be run to examine the relationships between years of professional experience, years of OS experience, level of OSPARK knowledge, and level of confidence. These correlations will be interpreted with a Bonferroni adjusted p -value of .0083. All statistical calculations and visualisations will be conducted in a programming language such as R, to make all the results reproducible.

For open-ended responses about training needs, a content analysis will be conducted. Researchers will collaboratively review a subset of responses (approximately 20% of the total dataset) to develop the initial coding framework. The existing codes used in Study 1 may be utilised in this process, if they are deemed to be relevant by the research team. Through discussion and consensus-building, the research team will establish definitions and boundaries for each code. A coding protocol will be developed to document these definitions, that will provide decision rules for ambiguous cases and will include illustrative examples of each code. All researchers will then independently code a different subset of responses (approximately 20% of the dataset) using the agreed-upon coding framework. Krippendorff's alpha will be calculated to quantify the level of agreement between coders; a threshold of $\alpha \geq 0.80$ will be considered acceptable. Discrepancies will be discussed until consensus is reached and the coding protocol will be updated accordingly. Once this acceptable inter-coder reliability is established, the remaining responses will be divided among the researchers for coding. The coding framework will be iteratively refined as analysis progresses, with new categories added or existing ones merged as appropriate. Regular meetings will be held throughout the coding process to maintain alignment and address any ambiguities that arise.

Study 3: Course evaluation

Study 3 aims to assess changes in knowledge and self-efficacy regarding marketing, communications, and outreach activities among open science advocates who participate in the OSPARK training programme (RQ4). It will also explore open science advocates' experiences of, and barriers to engaging in, outreach activities (RQ1), identify their training needs in relation to outreach, marketing, and communications (RQ2), and assess how knowledgeable and confident they are about core concepts in outreach activities before starting the training (RQ3). These data will be used to iterate on the OSPARK training programme, thereby improving its effectiveness and relevance to participants.

Method:

Data will be collected as part of in-person and online workshops, bootcamps, and email courses within the OSPARK programme. As this study is reliant on opportunity sampling of attendees, there is no formal target sample size, but the research team will aim to recruit approximately 30 participants.

Phase 1: Informed Consent

Informed consent will be obtained from participants as part of the event registration process. Participants will be directed to an online form which will provide information and collect informed consent for both the pre- and post-training questionnaires (see Appendices 7 and 8). Consent data will be stored independently of study data.

Phase 2: Pre-training Questionnaire

The questionnaire will include similar quantitative and qualitative elements as the Study 2 survey. However, the results of studies 1 and 2 may suggest the need to add new questions or modify existing ones to better capture emerging themes or areas of interest identified in those findings. The questionnaire will be conducted using Google Forms created within OLS's Google Workspace. Participants' data will be recorded anonymously, but they will be asked to generate a unique pseudonymous code to enable comparison of pre- and post-training datasets.

Phase 3: Post-training Questionnaire

The post-training questionnaire will include the same questions as the pre-training questionnaire to enable comparison of self-efficacy and knowledge before and after the training programme. Additionally, open-ended questions will be included to gather feedback about participants' training experiences, including what they learned, what aspects they found most valuable, and suggestions for improvement.

Analytic Plan:

Descriptive statistics will be calculated for all quantitative items in both the pre-training and post-training questionnaires. Frequencies and percentages will be computed for categorical variables and Likert-scale responses. Visualisations will be created to illustrate changes in self-efficacy and knowledge scores between the pre-training and post-training phases. Paired-samples t-tests will be conducted to determine whether observed differences in self-efficacy and knowledge are statistically significant and effect sizes (Cohen's *d*) will be calculated to quantify the magnitude of any observed changes. A post-hoc power analysis will also be conducted to estimate the probability of detecting an effect of the observed size. The research team will examine patterns within these visualisations and statistical results, with particular attention to the magnitude and direction of changes following the training programme. For calculating descriptive statistics, conducting statistical tests, and developing data visualisations, a programming language such as Python or R will be used to make all results reproducible.

A content analysis of open-ended responses will be conducted based on the method described by Braun and Clarke (2006). This will be an ongoing process, such that a mini-analysis will be conducted after each training cohort, but a final analysis will also take place which combines all data. The coding protocol developed during the analysis of survey responses will be applied to both pre-training and post-training questionnaire responses, ensuring consistency across data sources. The same researchers involved in coding the survey data will participate in this analysis to maintain continuity in interpretation and application of codes. For questions unique to the post-training questionnaire, new codes will be developed through a similar collaborative process as that used for the survey: researchers will review a sample of responses together, discuss and agree upon labels, update the coding protocol to add these new codes, and assess inter-coder reliability before proceeding to code the remainder of the data.

References

- Besley, J. C., Dudo, A., & Storksdieck, M. (2015). Scientists' views about communication training. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 52(2), 199–220. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21186>
- Boon, W., Haan, J. de, Duisterwinkel, C., Gould, L., Janssen, W., Jongsma, K., Milota, M., Radstake, M., Stevens, S., Strick, M., Swinkels, M., Mil, M. van, Sebille, E. van, Wanders, N., & Yerkes, M. A. (2022). Meaningful public engagement in the context of open science: Reflections from early and mid-career academics. *Research for All*, 6(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.14324/RFA.06.1.23>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Chen, G., Gully, S. M., & Eden, D. (2001). Validation of a new general self-efficacy scale. *Organizational research methods*, 4(1), 62–83. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109442810141004>
- Chuan-Peng, H., Xu, Z., Lazić, A., Bhattacharya, P., Seda, L., Hossain, S., Jeftić, A., Özdoğru, A. A., Amaral, O. B., Miljković, N., Ilchovska, Z. G., Lazarevic, L. B., Bao, H. W. S., Ghodke, N., Moreau, D., Elsherif, M., C., C., Ghai, S., Carneiro, C. F. D., ... Azevedo, F. (2025). Open Science in the Developing World: A Collection of Practical Guides for Researchers in Developing Countries. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 8(3), 25152459251357565. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459251357565>
- Cole, N. L., Kormann, E., Klebel, T., Apartis, S., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). The societal impact of Open Science: A scoping review. *Royal Society Open Science*, 11(6), 240286. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240286>
- Gagliardi, D., Cox, D., & Li, Y. (2015). Institutional Inertia and Barriers to the Adoption of Open Science. In E. Reale & E. Primeri (Eds), *The Transformation of University Institutional and Organizational Boundaries* (pp. 107–133). SensePublishers. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6300-178-6_6
- Havemann, J. (2023). *Mapping Open Science resources from around the world by discipline and principles*. Access 2 Perspectives. <https://doi.org/10.21428/51e64700.893d7337>
- Iley, B., Abdelkader, D., Afanaseva, A., Pereira Cardoso, J. F., Dierkes, J., Meesters, C., & Seibold, H. (2025). *Primer on Open Science Outreach* (Version 1). Open Science Retreat 2025, Beatenberg, Switzerland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15301862>
- Iley, B., Udoh, D., Yehudi, Y., Kao, J. Y., & Seibold, H. (2025, May 13). *How do you ensure your science is seen, used, and sustained?* Collaborations Workshop 2025 (CW25), Stirling,

Scotland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15681246>

Kao, J. Y., Yehudi, Y., Imming, M., & Seibold, H. (2025). *Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15148315>

Oates, J., Carpenter, D., Fisher, M., Goodson, S., Hannah, B., Kwaitkowski, R., Prutton, K., Reeves, D., & Wainwright, T. (2021). *BPS Code of Human Research Ethics*. British Psychological Society. <https://doi.org/10.53841/bpsrep.2021.inf180>

Poliakoff, E., & Webb, T. L. (2007). What Factors Predict Scientists' Intentions to Participate in Public Engagement of Science Activities? *Science Communication*, 29(2), 242–263. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547007308009>

Seibold, H., Iley, B., OLS, & Digital Research Academy. (2025, September 10). *Workbooks: Open Science on the Menu - How to get visibility for your Open Science Initiative*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093484>

Skubera, M., Korbmacher, M., Evans, T. R., Azevedo, F., & Pennington, C. R. (2025). International initiatives to enhance awareness and uptake of open research in psychology: A systematic mapping review. *Royal Society Open Science*, 12(3), 241726. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.241726>

UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMFH8546>

UNESCO. (2023). *Open science outlook 1: Status and trends around the world*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54677/GIIC6829>

Vicente-Saez, R., & Martinez-Fuentes, C. (2018). Open Science now: A systematic literature review for an integrated definition. *Journal of Business Research*, 88, 428–436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.12.043>

Zhang, Z., & Yuan, K.-H. (2018). *Practical Statistical Power Analysis Using Webpower and R* (Eds). ISDSA Press. <https://doi.org/10.35566/power>